

Potential of Solar Energy in Sudan*

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Abstract—This paper is meant to give a brief outlook on the potential of solar energy in Sudan and how to calculate it. First, the procedure of calculating the total irradiance based on real weather data is highlighted and the amount of energy generated per year is then calculated. Second, the orientation of a PV module in the capital city of Khartoum is discussed as well as the implication of the local weather on the module efficiency. Finally, the amount of electricity needed to satisfy the national demand is given based on these calculations and considering other losses in the system. The calculations are carried out using the current commercial photovoltaic technology available in the country.

Index Terms—Sudan, Solar Energy, Photovoltaic, Electricity, SNL, irradiance

I. INTRODUCTION

The sun produces a huge amount of energy through the process of nuclear fusion that has been burning for 4.6 billion years. This nuclear fusion emits all kinds of radiations, and the most useful radiation that reaches the earth is depicted in figure 1 and is known as the spectral radiance.

Fig. 1. Spectral radiance, AM0 measured outside the atmosphere, AM1.5 measured on the surface of the earth [1].

The radiance is a power density function that is wavelength-dependent, and the integration of the radiance yields, what came to be known as irradiance. The irradiance is the main unit that is used in solar energy calculation. It reflects the amount of energy received from the sun on an area of one square meter.

The earth's atmosphere is full of all kinds of particles that absorb and scatter the incident radiation. Therefore, for any

location, three types of irradiance are identified: The direct irradiance (G_{Direct}), the indirect diffused irradiance (G_{Diffuse})¹, and the indirectly reflected irradiance (G_{Albedo}). These components appear in the same order in equation (1).

$$G_{\text{total}} = DNI * \cos(AOI) + DHI * SVF + GHI * \alpha * (1 - SVF) \quad (1)$$

$$SVF = \frac{1 + \cos \theta_M}{2} \quad (2)$$

where:

- G_{total} = total irradiance
- DNI = direct normal irradiance
- AOI = angle of incidence
- DHI = diffuse horizontal irradiance
- SVF = sky view factor
- GHI = global horizontal irradiance
- α = albedo constant
- θ_M = module tilt angle

The total irradiance incident on any location depends on its coordinates and the time of the day. The typical pattern of the irradiance during the day follows the famous bell curve as shown in blue in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Solar irradiance during the day.

For the sake of simplifying the calculation, the unit of Equivalent Sun Hour (ESH) is adopted in most of the general

¹The Isotropic sky model is used here for calculating the diffused component.

calculations. ESH is calculated by aggregating G_{total} during the day and dividing it by 1000 W/m^2 .

II. IRRADIANCE CALCULATION

To calculate the potential of solar energy in Sudan, the capital city of Khartoum is taken as a representative of the country. The total irradiance is first calculated based on real data obtained from the famous software Meteonorm [2]. The software provides reliable and validated data collected between 1991 and 2010. The main three measurements used for calculating the irradiance components are shown in figure 3.

(a) The main variable of the direct irradiance component.

(b) The main variable of the diffused irradiance component.

(c) The main variable of the reflected irradiance component.

Fig. 3. The main measurements of the irradiance received on the capital city of Khartoum.

To calculate the total irradiance G_{total} , both the angle of incidence AOI and the module tilt θ_M are needed, however, since the calculation on this step is generalized for the entire

region, the modules are assumed to be on flat ground, shading free and always perpendicular to the sun azimuth (on the sun track from sunrise to sunset), i.e. both AOI and θ_M are 0° degree. Taking the albedo constant α to be 0.15, this yields the total irradiance shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4. Total irradiance throughout the year on the capital city of Khartoum.

This result gives an average of 7.8 ESH (7.8 Kwh/m^2) throughout the entire year, which is considered among the highest in the world, comparing this for instance to the Netherlands and Germany which both have an average of approximately 3 ESH [1], the solar potential is theoretically double in Sudan, and one could infer that the cost is, therefore, half for generating the same amount of energy during the day, as one would need twice the number of panels to substitute for having half sunshine during the day. However, to obtain more accurate figures, the variation of AOI , the effect of the weather and θ_M need to be considered.

III. THE MOVEMENT OF THE SUN

The angle of incidence AOI is simply the angle between the module perpendicular norm (normal n) and the sun's position in the sky. Thus, it varies throughout the day as well as during the year, i.e. daily and seasonal variation. The latter is however not very significant for Sudan as it is located near the equator, nevertheless, it will be taken into account. The equation for AOI is given in equation (3) and the angles are depicted in figure 5, [1]:

$$\cos(AOI) = \cos(a_M)\cos(a_S)\cos(A_M - A_S) + \sin(a_M)\sin(a_S) \quad (3)$$

Where:

a_M = altitude of the module = $90^\circ - \theta_M$

a_S = altitude of the sun

A_M = azimuth of the module

A_S = azimuth of the sun

The sun's path can be calculated independently for any location on earth, given its coordinates. To picture the movement of the sun observed from Khartoum (coordinates 15.5007° N 32.5599° E), figure 6 shows the variation of the sun path for four different months in the year. Another well-known figure to show the variation of the sun's path is the plot of

Fig. 5. Illustrating the angles used to describe the orientation of a PV module installed on a horizontal plane [1].

the Analemma. The Analemma is a diagram that shows the position of the sun in the sky as seen from a fixed location on earth at a specific time during the day during the year. The Analemma observed from Khartoum is shown in figure 7.

Fig. 6. The sun path as seen from Khartoum.

Fig. 7. The Analemma as seen from Khartoum.

IV. OPTIMAL ORIENTATION

The rule of thumb for PV module orientation is to direct it to face the equator with a tilt angle equals to the latitude of the location, for Khartoum this means directing the panels toward the south (azimuth equals 180° degree) with θ_M equals 15.5° degree. However, this is just an approximation, and in order to get the optimal orientation, equation (1) needs to be

evaluated for every possible orientation (azimuth and tilt) with a varying AOI and total irradiance for the whole year. Hence, the amount of irradiation received by the module is calculated for the entire year and the highest yield corresponds to the optimal orientation. This calculation is depicted in figure 8.

Fig. 8. Annual irradiation (Kwh/m^2) received on a PV module in Khartoum for every azimuth and tilt combination.

The result shows that the optimal module azimuth A_M is 203° degree and the optimal module tilt θ_M is 17° degrees. These settings give annual irradiation of $2290.9 Kwh/m^2$. It can be seen from figure 8 that there are multiple options for the module orientation that give the same maximum annual irradiation, this provides flexibility when engineering for different shading and roof constraints.

V. PV YIELD

To further calculate the accessible energy from the sun using the current commercial PhotoVoltaic (PV) technology, the **Cheetah 72M 380-400 Watt mono PERC** module is used for the specific parameters needed as it is available on the Sudanese market. The module (JKM400M-72) has an overall efficiency of 20.17% at Standard Test Conditions (STC). This efficiency changes with the temperature, the irradiance and the mounting structure of the module. Figure 9 shows the air temperature and wind speed in Khartoum, also obtained from the Meteornorm software and during the same period of the irradiance measurement.

Fig. 9. Temperature and wind speed measurements during the year in Khartoum.

The temperature effect on the module efficiency is calculated using the *Duffie-Beckman* model, which is described by equation (4). The estimated temperature of the module is then used along with the module parameters to calculate first the efficiency for varying irradiance (equations (5), (6), (7) and (8)) and then the overall efficiency for varying temperature (equation (9)).

$$T_M = T_a + \frac{T_{NOCT} - 20^\circ}{800} G_M \left(\frac{9.5}{5.7 + 3.8 \cdot w} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\eta_{STC}}{T \cdot \alpha} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$V_{OC}(25^\circ C, G_M) = V_{OC}(STC) + \frac{\eta k_B T_M}{q} \ln \left(\frac{G_M}{G_{STC}} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$I_{SC}(25^\circ C, G_M) = I_{SC}(STC) \frac{G_M}{G_{STC}} \quad (6)$$

$$P_{mpp}(25^\circ C, G_M) = FF \cdot V_{OC}(25^\circ C, G_M) \cdot I_{SC}(25^\circ C, G_M) \quad (7)$$

$$\eta(25^\circ C, G_M) = \frac{P_{mpp}(25^\circ C, G_M)}{G_M A_M} \quad (8)$$

$$\eta(T_M, G_M) = \eta(25^\circ C, G_M) [1 + k(T_M - 25^\circ C)] \quad (9)$$

where:

- T_M = temperature of the module
- T_a = temperature of the air
- T_{NOCT} = nominal operating cell temperature
- G_M = irradiance on the module
- w = wind speed
- η_{STC} = module efficiency in STC
- T = transmittance of the front layer of the module
- α = absorptivity of the module
- V_{OC} = open circuit voltage
- η = ideality/diode quality factor (1.2)
- k_B = Boltzmann constant
- I_{SC} = short circuit current
- FF = fill factor
- P_{mpp} = power at maximum power point
- A_M = area of a single module
- k = temperature coefficient

Following the given weather data and the total irradiance incident on the chosen model, figure 10 shows the effect of the weather on the module efficiency in the capital city of Khartoum. The chosen module experiences an average efficiency of 19.05% instead of its standard efficiency of 20.17%. Thus, the efficiency drops by 1.12% due to the temperature and irradiance variation on the location. The figure shows that indeed the efficiency is most likely to be lower during the summer as a result of the high temperature.

Fig. 10. PV module efficiency variation throughout the year in Khartoum.

VI. ELECTRICITY GENERATION

To estimate the electricity generated from PV modules, the DC power generated from the modules is given by equation (10). However, in practice, the equation is reversed: by knowing the demand/load power the required number of modules ($N_{modules}$) is calculated.

$$P_{PV} = \eta(T_M, G_M) * N_{modules} * G_M * A_M \quad (10)$$

where:

- P_{PV} = DC power of PV modules
- $N_{modules}$ = number of connected modules

To give a better estimation, the losses incorporated in the system are considered. The DC/AC inverter losses are the main losses in the system. The inverter efficiency varies with the input DC power and DC voltage. This variation is given by the Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) model as in the following equations [3]:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{AC}}{P_{DC}} \quad (11)$$

$$P_{AC} = \left[\frac{P_{AC0}}{A - B} - C(A - B) \right] (P_{DC} - B) + C(P_{DC} - B)^2 \quad (12)$$

$$A = P_{DC0} [1 + C_1(V_{DC} - V_{DC0})] \quad (13)$$

$$B = P_{S0} [1 + C_2(V_{DC} - V_{DC0})] \quad (14)$$

$$C = C_0 [1 + C_3(V_{DC} - V_{DC0})] \quad (15)$$

All the variables are manufacturer specific and described in [3], the only two variables are the operating V_{DC} and P_{DC} . For the sake of simplicity, the V_{DC} is assumed to be constant and regulated by the charge controller. The efficiency during the entire year is shown in figure 11, the average efficiency is found to be 90%.

The rest of the losses are approximately estimated as in figure 12. All the losses add up to account for 14% of the PV-generated electricity.

Fig. 11. Inverter Efficiency simulation based on SNL model.

Fig. 13. Electricity generated with PV technology to satisfy the annual demand for electricity in Sudan.

Fig. 12. Additional losses in a PV system.

[3] D. L. King, S. Gonzalez, G. M. Galbraith, and W. E. Boyson, "Performance model for grid-connected photovoltaic inverters," *Sandia National Laboratories SAND2007-5036*, 2007.

If the electricity demand in the country is considered to be 14,719 GWh as reported in 2018. The country would need a gigantic plant of 5.6 GW capacity (4 times the capacity of Merowe Dam, the largest dam in the country) to completely satisfy its electricity demand with solar energy by PV technology. In another figure, this would require 16,115,694 modules of the selected module in section V. This in turn would cover an area of 31.98 Km^2 (0.15% of the area of Khartoum) without considering the shading spacing. Finally, it is worth mentioning that currently, the largest PV power plant is the Pavagada Solar Park in Karnataka, India, with a capacity of 2.05 GW, two and a half of such a solar park would be required to cover the national demand of electricity in Sudan.

Figure 13 shows the hypothetical power plant and its PV electricity yield throughout the year. Needless to say, such a system would also require a huge amount of storage facility to flatten the curve and mitigate the solar intermittency during the day and the seasonal variation as well. This however could be tackled with hydro-power, but for a country like Sudan that suffers from transmission and distribution losses of more than 25%, small-scale distributed PV systems are preferred to satisfy each local consumption.

REFERENCES

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